

Effects and development of social media neologisms in English language and lexicographical level

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ANNOTATION

The topic of this discussion is about neologisms, which are very important in our lives due to the various developments that have occurred in the field of science and technology. There are also many new words that have been created in various fields. Given the above, it means that the topicality of this theme is very important.

Key words: Neologisms, science, technology, social media, onomasiological, lexical semantic meaning, well-ordered vocabulary, linguistic knowledge, linguistic, transformation, dictionary.

INTRODUCTION

The language used in social networks is unique, as people interact, they form new words in their social groups so that they can communicate effectively. Social media, being part of the technology, means that they evolve as well as the language used. Neologisms are produced every day to name new objects, things and ideas. This study focuses on the use of English neologisms in social networks, so understanding the concept of social networks is crucial. Social media provide a social channel for the virtual interaction of their users, namely those who often use social networks for communication. Social networks turn into a personal tool, which people use talking with family and friends. But they were subsequently adopted by enterprises that wanted to use the popular new method of communication to attract customers: inform them about sales and offer them special sales and, in fact, collection reviews of their products and services.

MAIN PART

Effects of Neologisms on English language. We will be focusing on only social media neologisms so words examined only will be the coined through the social networking online. Because it involves internet, computers and mobile phones and language development so it can't be carried under on linguistics theory. The theory of Computer-Mediated Communications will focus on the aspects of internet and social media use. An onomasiological theory will explore the processes of word-formation of the neologisms, while the theory of lexical semantics will explain the meanings of the neologisms.

Now we will see what scholars have said about the main concepts of social media neologisms. The subject of our study is the spreading system of neologism in lexical system of modern English language as a result of online social networking and what changes they have brought in the language.

a) The change in English language vocabulary

Henry Fowler, in his book **Modern English Usage**, states thus: “*The gift of speech and a well-ordered vocabulary are characteristic of every known language group*”.

Words are the basic elements of every language; thus, they are the medium by which changes occur in a language. The vocabulary is thus said to be the first point of contact in the process of language change. The vocabulary of a language, the totality of its words, is also called its lexicon. So, we can divide a language into two categories: the lexical and the grammatical. A grammar is a system of rules or regularities in a language, and a lexicon a collection of linguistic knowledge that cannot be captured by rules. The lexicon is organized into lexical entries; each of these lexical entries collects the appropriate information about a particular linguistic expression called a lexeme. Lexical words refer to reality in our physical and mental worlds and consist chiefly of nouns, verbs and adjectives; while grammatical words express relationships within the language itself and include conjunctions, pronouns, prepositions and articles. The term used for lexical words is ‘lexeme’, which is the designation for the kind of item which is listed and clearly defined in a dictionary. So, we can say that lexeme is a basic lexical unit of a language, consisting of one word or several words, considered as an abstract unit, and applied to a family of words related by form or meaning.

At times we will be dealing with a lexeme made up of more than one words, so lexeme can consist of more than one-word form. For example, both ‘perambulator’ and ‘baby carriage’ are single lexemes. Where a lexeme has more than one distinct meaning, we can talk about each combination of the lexeme and a particular meaning as a lexical unit. So, neologisms can be classified as the lexemes which have their own meaning in particular community or speech.

Language changes with the passage of time and evolves and gets developed. Thus, English language has also changed with addition of new words, by changing meanings of old words etc. The central point in the development of the English language is the enrichment and enlargement of its vocabulary. The newly created words after a certain period of time being perceived as unusual and new enter the stock of the English lexicon as its integral part. And it is words that make the changes in the language noticeable and evident.

b) Gradual linguistic transformation and development

It is words that make the changes in the language noticeable and evident. In Modern English, vocabulary change is often socially problematic. As people observe language change, they usually react negatively, feeling that the language has gone downhill, that

language change is functionally disadvantageous, in that it hinders communication. In modern society, those who use the social media are more conversant with the neologisms that have arisen as a result. Such neologisms are sometimes also negatively evaluated by socially dominant groups. However, the linguistic pessimists who view the English language in this way are concerned about several factors: supposedly decreasing standards of literacy marked by poor spelling and grammatically incomplete or incorrect sentences; the use of informal spoken language in written contexts; allegedly inaccurate pronunciation; and the way in which international forms of English may affect English language in the future. But whatever linguists feel about the effects social, cultural and worldwide changes have on language, if the changes are useful, they will probably survive. So, we can Change is at the heart of a living language and by embracing it rather than fearing it, language users can benefit from the diversity that linguistic flexibility offers.

c) English for specific purpose

According to **Oxford English Dictionary** editor **Angus Stevenson**, “Social networking sites have created a real language of the net.” (*The Telegraph*, Sept. 25, 2010).

Lynn Cherny [1999] concludes that “the linguistic interaction using social media is most amenable to description in terms of register,” and **Davis** and **Brewer** [1997], in their study of chat groups, conclude that “it has come to be seen as a register; language for a specific purpose.”

The present research agrees with this as the development of new words in social networking has led to the development of the specialist vocabulary known as the social media register. The current researchers consider this approach to be more profound as it takes into consideration not only the fact of the appearance of a new word form, but also the changes of its internal and external organization. Examples are social media neologisms such as friend, like, web, net and unlike which have assumed new meanings.

we can divide neologisms into there are the three types of neologisms, the first class includes only those *lexemes which have not existed up to a certain period of time*, i.e. cannot be found in the texts written before a given moment. Thus, it includes the smallest number of lexical units. For example, such words as ‘googling’, ‘Facebooking’ ‘blogging’ had not existed even in the first half of the 1900s.

The second class represents the *words that have changed their meaning but retained their old form*, with their old meaning lost or moved towards secondary importance, e.g. slum, bread,

salt, etc. These units are the results of ‘secondary nomination’.

The third class contains those lexemes which have only added one or more new meanings without losing the significance of the old ones; they present the paradigmatic relations of polysemy, for instance, surf, file, mouse, report, etc.

This study embraces all types of neologisms. We will analyze types of lexemes in the etymology aspect and additionally, we discuss how new words are formed, their semantic meaning in context.

d) Neologisms and the Dictionary

C. Paul Cook in his research paper *Exploiting linguistic knowledge to infer properties of*, suggests that First, neologisms formed by the addition or combination of elements, especially compounding, affixation, blending and acronymization. Second, neologisms formed by reduction of elements, namely, abbreviations, backformation and shortenings -Third, neologisms that are neutral with respect to addition or reduction: semantic change, coinages, conversion or loans. In his theories of word-formation in the English language.

So, a neologism can be said to be a word which has lost the status of a nonce-formation but is still one which is considered new by the majority of the members of a speech community. This description already presupposes a certain distribution and frequency of the item in question. However, this study reveals that it is not only the frequency of a word at a certain time that is important, but also its permanent frequency over a certain period of time, and above all, its distribution in various communicative contexts and domains. It was according to these and other factors that the *publisher of Merriam-Webster* selected the neologisms to appear in the supplements of *Webster's Third New International Dictionary*.

CONCLUSION

Neologisms in social networks are fascinating to read on social networking sites. Standard English is normal and looks monotonous, users of social networks choose neologisms so that their posts and messages can attract a large audience. Social networking neologisms help users of social networking sites keep abreast of an evolving language. Some people are left behind due to the neologisms used every day, while other users' despair about how using this informal environment can lead to an equally random attitude towards grammar. Social networks provide a rich platform for experimentation, development and undermining of the language. This is a great way to keep up with the changes, paying attention to discussions on social networks, and you can notice the appearance of new words, the new use of words.

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